

White stem borer (WSB) effect on upland yield

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We studied the effect of WSB *Scirpophaga innotata* on upland rice with seven levels of protection in an experiment at the Makariki Experimental Farm, Seram Island, May-Aug 1982. IR36 was planted in a 5 × 5 m plot at 25 × 25 cm plant spacing in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications. Fertilizers as urea, TSP, and KCl were applied at 120 kg N, 40 kg P, and 50 kg K/ha. Half the N and all the P and K were applied in the row at the side of the plants 7 d after planting (DP). Half the N was applied 40 DP.

Yield loss caused by WSB *S. innotata* under upland conditions. Makariki, Seram Island, Indonesia, 1982.

Treatment ^a	WSB damage ^b (%)				Grain yield (t/ha)	Yield loss ^c (%)
	3 WP	5 WP	7 WP	9 WP		
1. Complete protection	7.2	1.2	1.5	1.9	2.4	—
2. Complete protection minus a	11.4	1.5	2.0	2.3	2.4	1.7
3. Complete protection minus b	21.9	7.9	4.4	3.3	1.8	25.6
4. Complete protection minus c	24.2	8.9	2.7	3.3	1.8	25.6
5. Complete protection minus d	14.4	2.1	3.4	3.3	2.3	5.8
6. Recommended ^d protection	12.5	2.2	2.3	2.6	2.2	9.1
7. No protection (control)	39.2	15.5	8.6	9.7	1.8	26.9
LSD (0.05)	2.7	1.2	0.6	0.6	0.4	—
CV (%)	9.7	14.6	11.2	9.9	14.6	—

^a a = seed treatment with carbaryl 85 S, b = carbofuran 3G (10 DP) + diazinon 60 EC (21 DP), c = carbofuran 3G (42 DP) + diazinon 60 EC (63 DP), d = monocrotophos 15 WSC. ^b WP = weeks after planting. ^c Compared with complete protection. Carbofuran 3G (10 DP) + diazinon 60 EC (when deadhearts exceeded 10%).

WSB damage at active tillering 3 wk after planting was high, an average 39.2% in control (see table). As plants grew, damage decreased.

Complete protection yielded 2.4 t/ha,

significantly higher than control, no protection during active tillering (treatment 3), and no protection at booting (treatment 4). □

Weed management

Effect of herbicides on *Ischaemum rugosum*

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Ischaemum rugosum Salisb., reported to be a major weed of partially irrigated and rainfed lowland rice in Thailand, Sri Lanka, and the Philippines, is very competitive against rice.

We designed a greenhouse experiment to study the effect of some herbicides on growth of *I. rugosum* under dry seeded and wet seeded conditions. There were 12 treatments in the dry seeded trial and 9 treatments in the wet seeded (see table). The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with six replications.

Plant height and shoot dry weight were measured 6 wk after seeding. Under dry seeded conditions, both plant height and shoot dry weight were reduced by all the herbicides at all application times (see table). Even though propanil applied at the two- and

Effect of different herbicide treatments on shoot dry weight and height of *I. rugosum* 6 wk after seeding under simulated dry seeded and wetland conditions. ^a

Herbicide and application rate (kg ai/ha)	Time of application	Shoot weight (mg/plant)	Plant height (mm)
<i>Dry seeded</i>			
Butachlor (2.0)	Preemergence	0.6 b	5 ab
	1-leaf	2.9 d	22 c
	2-leaf	5.0 f	48 d
Thiobencarb (3.0)	Preemergence	1.2 c	7 ab
	1-leaf	3.3 de	24 c
	2-leaf	4.3 ef	46 d
Pendimethalin (2.0)	Preemergence	0.4 a	3 a
	1-leaf	3.0 d	22 c
	2-leaf	5.6 b	44 d
Propanil (2.0)	2-leaf	1.4 c	43 d
	3-leaf	0.5 ab	18 bc
Untreated	—	21.6 g	247 d
<i>Wetland</i>			
Butachlor (1.0)	Preemergence	0 a	—
	1-leaf	119.9 c	42 a
	2-leaf	119.6 c	54 b
Thiobencarb (1.0)	Preemergence	0 a	—
	1-leaf	112.7 bc	44 a
	2-leaf	67.2 b	52 b
Propanil (2.0)	2-leaf	0 a	—
	3-leaf	0 a	—
Untreated	—	124.6 c	156 c

^a In a column under each condition, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.